

Batteries & Supercaps

Supporting Information

Unveiling True Limits of Electrochemical Performance of Organic Cathodes in Multivalent Batteries through Cyclable Symmetric Cells

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Synthesis of magnesium tetrakis(hexafluoroisopropoxy)borate

Mg(BH₄)₂ was synthesized through a published procedure^[1] and dissolved (5 mmol) in 10 mL of DME. HFIP (8.5 eq., 42 mmol) was dropwise added into the stirred solution. After 20 h of stirring at room temperature, the solution was concentrated under a vacuum and added into hexane to precipitate salt. Salt was filtered and dried under a vacuum at 50 °C for 2 days.

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 4.68–4.59 (m, 8H), 3.42 (s, 12H), 3.23 (s, 18H).

¹⁹F NMR (565 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ -74.25 (d, *J* = 6.3 Hz).

Figure S1. Infrared spectra of Mg[B(hfip)₄]₂ salt.

Synthesis of calcium tetrakis(hexafluoroisopropoxy)borate

Ca(BH₄)₂·2THF (2.5 mmol) was dissolved in 5 mL of DME. HFIP (8 eq., 20 mmol) was dropwise added into the stirred solution. After 20h of stirring at room temperature, salt was isolated from the reaction mixture with salt precipitation from hexane. Salt was filtered and dried under a vacuum at 50 °C for 2 days.

¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 4.64 (m, 8H), 3.42 (s, 16H), 3.23 (s, 24H).

¹⁹F NMR (565 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ -74.23 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz).

Figure S2. Infrared spectra of Ca[B(hfip)₄]₂ salt.

Poly(anthraquinonyl sulfide) synthesis

PAQS/CNT composite was prepared through a modified published procedure.^[2] 595 mg of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) were dispersed in 300 ml of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) (ultrasonic tip, ice bath, 2 h).

Na₂S·xH₂O was first submitted to azeotropic distillation in toluene and then dried under vacuum for 24 h (50 °C). Obtained Na₂S (1.95 g, 25 mmol) and 1,5-dichloroanthraquinone (6.93 g, 25 mmol) were added to the MWCNTs dispersion in NMP, and the solution was bubbled with nitrogen (20 minutes). The mixture was then left to react overnight at 200 °C under constant stirring and a static nitrogen atmosphere. The product was filtered, washed with hot water and acetone several times, and dried at 120 °C under a vacuum for 12 h. A total of 5.96 g (91% yield) of black powder was obtained (PAQS with 10 wt% MWCNTs).

Figure S3. Schematic of PAQS synthesis and infrared spectra of synthesized PAQS composite.

Cycling stability of PAQS-anode half-cells (anode = metal Li, Mg, Ca) at C/2

Figure S4. Cycling stability and Coulombic efficiency for PAQS/CNT cathode versus lithium, magnesium, and calcium at C/2, for first 100 cycles. Coulombic efficiency for the calcium system is shown only for the initial 6 cycles performed.

Coulombic efficiency has been calculated as capacity obtained in discharge divided by capacity obtained in charge. The first discharge has been omitted from efficiency calculations.

Calculation of the true capacity utilization of the active material (PAQS) by considering capacitive contribution of carbon black conductive additive

It is well known that (electronically) conductive electrode additive(s) that constitute the electrode composite also partially contribute to the total measured capacity of the tested battery electrode. In general, at all the surface of the electronically conductive phase that is accessible to (“wetted with”) electrolyte, there is a formation of an electrical double layer with the corresponding capacitive contribution. During a normal charging/discharging process of the inspected electrode, there is in parallel an additional charge stored at the interface that gives overestimated values of an active material capacity. One of the most common conductive additives are various types of carbon black as well as other carbon materials (e.g. carbon fibers). One of the most reliable approaches to determine the corresponding excessive capacity of carbon black is to perform galvanostatic measurement of the stored charge under the same conditions applied in the active material testing (the same electrolyte, and same voltage span). Such an evaluation is for the case of Printex XE2 carbon black in 1 M LiTFSI DOL:DME (1:1, v:v) shown in Figure S5. For the particular case of the tested PAQS cathode shown in **Figure 1a** the values are: $m(\text{composite}) = 3.7 \text{ mg}$, $m(\text{PAQS}) = 2.0 \text{ mg}$, $m(\text{Printex}) = 1.1 \text{ mg}$. From **Figure**

S5 we read out the measured specific capacity of Printex in the used voltage window to be around 30 mAh g⁻¹. By considering the ratios between PAQS active material and Printex, we can approximate the Printex XE2 capacity contribution to be 16 mAh g⁻¹.

Figure S5. Galvanostatic discharge/charge curve for Printex XE2 : PTFE (70 : 30 wt%) electrode at 50 mAh g⁻¹ in 1 M LiTFSI DOL:DME (1:1, v:v) with Li metal as counter electrode.

Thus, when the carbon black contribution is taken into consideration, the true obtained capacity of PAQS material in the composite cathode in the lithium half-cell (**Figure 1a**) is 207 instead of 223 mAh g⁻¹. Accordingly, the true capacity utilization of PAQS active material relative to the theoretical value (225 mAh g⁻¹) for the case shown in **Figure 1a** is: $(207/225) \times 100\% = 92\%$. For more details about the correction and calculation applied see also reference.^[3]

Voltage hysteresis of the PAQS-anode half-cells (metal anode: Li, Mg, and Ca)

Figure S6. Evolution of magnitude of the voltage hysteresis of the PAQS-anode half-cells (metal anode: Li, Mg, and Ca) during initial 100 cycles obtained at C/2 in lithium, magnesium, and calcium system.

EIS of symmetric anode-anode cells assembled from metal anodes (Li, Mg, Ca)

Figure S7. Nyquist plot of measured PEIS spectra of symmetric anode-anode cells assembled from the metal anodes (Li, Mg, Ca) obtained from the corresponding initial PAQS-anode half-cells disassembled at SoC = 0.5. Full frequency span (1 MHz – 1 mHz) is shown in a) and high-frequency part in b). Measurements were performed in 1 M LiTFSI DOL:DME (1:1, v:v) for the Li-Li cell, in 0.2 M Mg[B(hfip)₄]₂ DME for the Mg-Mg cell, and in 0.2 M Ca[B(hfip)₄]₂ DME for the Ca-Ca cell.

Preparation of cyclable cathode-cathode symmetric cells

Figure S8. Schematic representation of the preparation of cyclable cathode-cathode cells used in this work. The initial cathode-metal half-cell with cathode A was after discharge disassembled and paired with additional (pristine) cathode B to form a cyclable B(+)||A(-) symmetric cell. Both cyclable symmetric cells and half-cells were assembled by using two-electrode Swagelok type setup with stainless steel casing.

Comparison of galvanostatic voltage hysteresis of PAQS-Li cell and corresponding cyclable symmetric PAQS-PAQS cell

Figure S9. Measured galvanostatic voltage hysteresis of PAQS-Li cell and cyclable symmetric (+) PAQS II PAQS-M (-) cell with 1 M LiTFSI in DOL/DME obtained at C/5 rate with corresponding reactions taking place during charge and discharge of the cells.

The hysteresis parameters of PAQS-Li cell and symmetric PAQS-PAQS cell (Figure 3 in the main text)

The difference in the magnitude of voltage hysteresis of half of the symmetric PAQS-PAQS cell ($0.5 \times 219 \text{ mV} = 109.5 \text{ mV}$) and hysteresis magnitude of PAQS-Li cell (116 mV) with a value of around 6 mV can be explained by considering the overpotential of the Li metal anode. For this purpose, it is first deduced from **Figure S7b** that the typical total impedance of a symmetric Li-Li cell in 1 M LiTFSI in DOL/DME is about 50Ω . Accordingly, for the PAQS-Li half-cell, which includes a single lithium anode, the corresponding resistance is about half of the value for Li-Li cell ($R(\text{Li}) = 25 \Omega$). We just give an estimation for the Li anode overpotential by assuming that the Li anode impedance (resistance) does not change when under current bias and by simply applying Ohms law: $\Delta V(\text{Li}) = I \cdot R(\text{Li})$. For the particular case shown in **Figure 3** one obtains: $\Delta V(\text{Li}) = 25 \Omega \cdot 87 \mu\text{A} (\text{C}/5) = 2.2 \text{ mV}$. Charge-discharge voltage hysteresis of PAQS-Li cell includes 2-times anode overpotential contribution (one for charge and one for discharge direction). Thus, one finds a similar magnitude of the additional overpotential ($2 \times 2.2 \text{ mV} = 4.4 \text{ mV}$) as presented above (6 mV) and expected from the consideration

of the experimental data shown in **Figure 3**. Importantly, the simple analysis given above provides a direct explanation for the small experimental deviation between the overpotential of a single PAQS electrode in the PAQS-Li half-cell and the overpotential of a single cathode in the corresponding symmetric PAQS cell. Similar consideration can be applied for explanation of the observed small deviation of the magnitude of the voltage curve slope of the PAQS-Li cell and half of the magnitude of the PAQS cell at SoC = 0.5, shown in **Figure 3**.

Galvanostatic voltage hysteresis of cyclable PAQS-PAQS symmetric cells at low rate (C/5)

Figure S10. Comparison of measured galvanostatic voltage hysteresis of cyclable (+) PAQS II PAQS-M (-) symmetric cells at C/5 obtained in lithium, magnesium, and calcium electrolyte.

Rate performance and voltage hysteresis of cyclable symmetric PAQS-PAQS organic cells

Figure S11. Comparison of rate performance of PAQS-anode half-cells and corresponding cyclable symmetric cells with lithium and magnesium electrolyte, respectively. Note that, due to the severe calcium anode passivation, rate capability in calcium half-cell was not possible to perform, and therefore calcium is not presented in this graph.

Figure S12. Comparison of magnitude of the voltage hysteresis of cyclable (+) PAQS II PAQS-M (-) symmetric cells as a function of C-rate obtained in lithium, magnesium, and calcium electrolyte.

Table S1. Comparison of measured voltage hysteresis, (total) overpotential, and capacity of PAQS cathodes in the PAQS-anode half-cells and in the corresponding symmetric (+) PAQS II PAQS-M (-) cells for several selected rates: C/2, 1C, 5C, and 50C. Values are taken from the third cycle (last cycle) at specific C-rate. The values given in the table do not include C/5 rate because of the irreversibility, reflected in poor Coulombic efficiency, of Mg half-cells. Missing values for Ca half-cells are inaccessible because of the poor cyclability of Ca metal anode.

	C-rate	PAQS-anode Half-cell			PAQS-PAQS Symmetric cell		
		Hysteresis (mV)	Overpotential (mV)	Capacity (mAhg ⁻¹)	Hysteresis (mV)	Overpotential (mV)	Capacity (mAhg ⁻¹)
Li	C/2	114	56	218	214	54	207
	1C	118	59	213	216	54	202
	5C	175	89	189	243	61	187
	50C	753	376	63	417	104	147
Ca	C/2	590	295	116	389	97	118
	1C	-	-	-	400	200	94
	5C	-	-	-	517	129	66
	50C	-	-	-	788	197	39
Mg	C/2	779	389	133	627	157	153
	1C	783	391	122	661	165	130
	5C	772	383	71	763	191	92
	50C	1114	557	21	1082	270	51

Determination of the values of voltage hysteresis and slope of the measured galvanostatic curves

Below in **Figures S14** and **R15** there are shown the results of linear regression analysis for the PAQS-Li and (+)PAQS//PAQS-M(-) cells that appear in the **Figure 3** of the main text. The analysis was done in the central part of the voltage curves ($95 - 120 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$) where the measured curves are indeed very close to linear (**Figure S13**) and consequently the reading of the hysteresis value and slope determination is straightforward. Moreover, this observation confirms that the chosen PAQS model material is indeed appropriate for the precise studies of voltage hysteresis (hysteresis magnitude and voltage slope) of organic active materials.

Figure S13. The central part ($95 - 120 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$) of the measured voltage curves of PAQS-Li (a) and (+)PAQS//PAQS-M(-) (b) cells obtained in 1 M LiTFSI in DOL/DME at C/5. The curves exhibit very close to linear dependence vs. capacity.

Results of the linear regression show only minute deviation of measured curves from an ideal linear dependence; standard error of slope determination is typically in the order of 0.1 %. On the other hand there is a slight difference in the value of the slope for both directions of applied current. Accordingly the reported values of slope in the main text are the average of the two individual readings and the reported error is the deviation between those two values. For example, in the case of the PAQS-Li cell the two values are 2.14 and 2.09 mV/mAhg^{-1} ; the reported value is $(2.11 \pm 0.05) \text{ mV/mAhg}^{-1}$, showing the relative deviation of about 2.4 %. And in the case of the (+)PAQS//PAQS-M(-) cell the two values are 4.21 and 4.08 mV/mAhg^{-1} ; the reported value is $(4.14 \pm 0.13) \text{ mV/mAhg}^{-1}$, showing the relative deviation of about 3.1 %.

Figure S14. Results of linear regression analysis of measured galvanostatic charge (a) and discharge (b) voltage curves of the PAQS-Li cell for the central part of the curves (in the range 95 – 120 mAh g⁻¹).

Figure S15. Results of linear regression analysis of measured galvanostatic positive current (a) and negative current (b) voltage response curves of the (+)PAQS||PAQS-M(-) cell for the central part of the curves (in the range 95 – 120 mAh g⁻¹).

References

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